

The Detection of New Store Openings Using Spatial Interaction Models

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Summary

This paper reports on the development of a large scale spatial interaction model using loyalty card data from a major UK grocery retailer, with the aim of being able to predict the location of new stores opening. We cover the implementation of the model, the choices of data adjustments, current model performance and the effects of new store openings on existing stores.

KEYWORDS: Spatial Interaction Model, Gravity Model, Poisson Regression, Loyalty Card, Retailing

1. Background and Project Rationale

This paper reports on the initial phases (model building and data exploration) of the development of a Spatial Interaction Model designed to be able to accurately predict store revenue and simulate the effects of new store openings on existing stores. This project is undertaken in conjunction with dunnhumby, with access to a major UK grocery retailers loyalty card scheme spanning the entirety of the UK across several years.

Recent challenges in the grocery retailing market grocery store location and size have developed around increasing competition and potential saturation in domestic markets, the shift towards convenience culture by consumers and the growth of e-commerce platforms. The first of these has developed in relation to continuing questions over domestic grocery market saturation that have been periodically raised (Butler, 2012), and is especially topical given the significant expansion plans of discounters such as Aldi and Lidl over the next five years (Nazir, 2021). In terms of convenience culture however, this has mostly manifested itself in the form of convenience stores which are smaller than 3,000 sqft and are located close to consumers homes or workplaces with a wide but shallow product range. This is to the extent that most of the increase in grocery stores nationwide from 2002-2012 was of this format from retailers such as Co-op, Tesco and Sainsbury’s (Hood, et al., 2015). Finally, while the rise of e-commerce that has permeated many other markets much quicker than grocery retailing, it is starting to gain a foothold in the market (Kiby-Hawkins, et al., 2019), driven by the benefits to the consumer of reduced search costs, no travel costs and restrictions on shopping hours (Hamad & Schmitz, 2019), which has since been accelerated by the pandemic.

Current research has begun to tackle the issues of integrating convenience shopping and e-commerce into spatial interaction models. For example, Hood et al., (2015) classified convenience stores in Yorkshire and the Humber based on their local environment, while Waddington, et al., (2018) was able to accurately predict convenience store revenue by building on earlier work by Newing et al., (2015) and allowing for demand estimations for office workers and students. As for integrating e-commerce sales into the retail gravity model, Beckers et al., (2021) invert the traditional distance deterrence term

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in the model and see resulting increases in modelling accuracy. However there remains a gap in analysing the effects of competing stores and being able to use these models to predict where and when they open. In this regard, while there is considerable opportunities for data collection in the UK relating to competitors, in other international markets the data is not always so easily available. Thus, the aim is to develop a model based on the UK market to simulate the location of new opening stores for which the modelling practice could then be adopted in other markets where data on competitors is not as freely available or the market moves much quicker.

2. Current model results

The current model we have developed trains on a single region in the UK and focuses solely on large stores (those over 10,000 sqft) within the region as it is acknowledged that the spatial interaction model in its current form struggles with predicting revenue for smaller stores (Waddington, et al., 2018). This is done using loyalty card data for a major grocery retailer in the UK using Poisson Regression from the statsmodels.api library. The data provided here comes in the form of the value of sales and the number of households shopping at a given store from output areas in the UK.

The loyalty card spend itself can be separated into different categories across departments which has allowed the model to be trained exclusively on food and non-food grocery revenue. This is because these larger format stores allow square footage to be devoted to other non-grocery revenue streams such as clothing or technology, where here we are focused on grocery revenue. While the model is trained on this grocery revenue dataset, the parameters are extracted and the revenue is then scaled up using the model formula of:

$$T_{ij} = A_i O_i^k W_j^{\alpha^k} d_{ij}^{-\beta^k} \quad (1)$$

Where:

$$A_i = \frac{1}{\sum_j W_j^{\alpha^k} d_{ij}^{-\beta^k}} \quad (2)$$

Here, T_{ij} denotes the flow of revenue from origin (i), to destination (j), O_i^k is the grocery revenue available at origin (i) from supergroup (k), W_j is the attractiveness of the store as given by store size and sqft, and d_{ij} is the distance between the origin and destination. Here α represents the attractiveness parameter and β the distance decay parameter which are disaggregated according to each output area supergroup.

In this case, estimates for grocery revenue available per output area were obtained by the number of households from the 2011 census data combined with estimates household spend on groceries from the living costs and food survey such that:

$$O_i^k = e^k n_i \quad (3)$$

Where O_i^k is a measure of total expenditure available in origin i by household type k during the year, with e^k is a measure of the average weekly grocery spend for a household in supergroup k, while n_i is a measure of the number of households in origin i.

Using these models over a whole year in 2017, we can see from figure 1 below that the ability of the model to estimate the total revenue of the stores in the region varies across the year, highlighted by the significant underprediction during the periods of Easter, the summer holidays and the Christmas period. However this is a well known issue, as highlighted by Newing et al., (2015), and thus we can see from the weeks where these influences are not evident that we are close to estimating the total revenue in the system, at least in terms of residential demand within these stores.

Figure 1 Weekly total revenue estimates for UK national grocery chain

However, even though we are able to accurately estimate total residential revenue within the system, the model currently struggles in its ability to predict individual store revenue. This can be seen in the figure below whereby although the average store error is 3.30%, some stores are over predicted by up to 60% while others are underpredicted by up to 40%. Thus, model improvements are expected to be brought in to try to balance that error and improve the model before simulation work can begin.

Figure 2 Store level revenue errors for a single week

3. New store openings

Within this model it is expected that the expenditure at a store is determined by not only the revenue available within output areas nearby, the size of the store and the distance to the store but also the competitors around it. Thus, if a new competitor opened up within the competitive range of an existing store than it is expected that revenue may be negatively effected due to drawing revenue away from output areas nearby. We have been able to visualise this effect by plotting the mean change in revenue of all stores that have a store open near them within a 2017 across a range of distances for both loyalty card and total revenue.

Figure 3 Changes in total and loyalty card revenue around the weeks of a new store opening

We can see here that in the week the new store opens (week 0) we see a dip in both loyalty card and total revenue that is greater than any of the changes 10 weeks before or after the new store opens. We can also see that this effect is stronger the closer the new store is which in line with what the spatial interaction model formulation would suggest. The hope is that we will be able to use these effects to simulate the opening of new stores using the spatial interaction model formulation. This will be enabled by the changes in loyalty card data where we will be able to see from which output areas these changes come from as well.

4. Conclusions

While these results show the beginning of model development and a visualisation of the effects of new stores, there is still a long way to go before effective simulations can be made. It is expected that new open source datasets will be integrated into the model in the future to supplement the attractiveness measures to be able to allow this model to generalise to other countries and for the errors in individual stores to be ironed to allow for more accurate models in the future. The hope is to also extend this model to convenience stores, in line with the research by Waddington et al., (2018), given their increase in prominence in the UK and their importance for competitiveness.

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